

The Impact from Social Capital of University on the Cultivation of Student Quality

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Abstract

Students' quality is the core competitiveness of universities, and the cultivation of students' quality not only depends on the school's teaching and research level, but also on the university's social capital. In this paper, Social capital of university is classified into structural social capital, relation social capital and cognitive social capital. These points are put forward which structural social capital influences the cultivation of student by providing social practice opportunity, relationship social capital affecting it by these activities organized by student organization, cognitive social capital influencing it through the culture of universities.

Keywords: structural social capital; relation social capital; cognitive social capital; cultivation of student

1. Introduction

In recent years, the number of candidates for China's college entrance examination are decreasing year by year. It is more and more common for children from middle or above class families to study abroad. Battle for outstanding students is becoming the competition among universities. The cultivation of students is the core of universities, the quality of Universities students is one of the core competitiveness of Universities, which is not only related to teaching level, but also related to the combination of teaching equipment, teaching and research, and the quality of the students. Social capital is a collection of actual or potential resources that an individual can obtain from a network of relationships (Bourdieu, 1986), It is created as a social relationship or a social structure of the relationship that can

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bring resources (Coleman, 1988). With the in-depth research of the social capital, more and more research pay attention to the social capital of organization, including government, universities. This paper intends to discuss how the social capital of universities impacts the cultivation of student quality.

2. Classification of social capital in Universities

According to the viewpoint of Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998), social capital is a kind of trust and cooperation which is brought about by the development of interpersonal network, it is divided into three levels: structural social capital, relational social capital and cognitive social capital. The structural social capital mainly includes the network joint and the network structure of the social relations, the network structure, the available social organization relations; the cognitive social capital mainly includes the common vision, the common language symbol, and the shared narrative. According to these three aspects, this paper divides the social capital of Universities into structural social capital, relational social capital and cognitive social capital, which are showed in figure 1. The three type's capital influence each other mutually, being embedded in the internal network of University, which is an important source of university competitive advantage. It influences the school in the process of teaching, scientific research and social service activities.

Figure 1: the composition of social capital in Universities

2.1 Structural social capital in universities

The social capital of Universities is mainly manifested in the internal and external network, such as the strength of the connection, the density of the network, the location of the individual in the network, etc. The relationship networks and their characteristics determine the quantity and quality of access to information and resources. The strength of interpersonal relationships, the size of the network density and the location of the network will affect the speed and quality of information and resource. There are two kinds of social relations network, which are horizontal and vertical. Horizontal network refers to the cooperation among peers, For example, cooperation among universities, as well as cooperation among universities and research institutes, financial institutions, as well as among various teams within the university. This kind of horizontal connection is similar to the strong relationship, and the cooperation between two parties and the establishment of the relationship are based on certain common characteristics, for example, common values, common interests or common resources and equipment. Vertical relation network refers to the relationship between higher education institutions and its higher administrative departments, which are often weak. "No matter how dense, no matter how important to the participants, cannot maintain social trust and cooperation" (Putnam, 2001), But the information and resources provided by the connect are often different from the information

and resources by their own, therefore, universities can make contact with a lot of different social resources, the success of the establishment of cooperative behavior, often have more chance of success.

Structural social capital is a role and social network based on rules and procedures, it can promote collective action and create collective benefits, and can be improved by the group's conscious action. The reason why the social capital of universities can promote the development of themselves is not only that they can obtain all kinds of tangible and intangible resources, but also in the construction of the network. The role of various social roles, strengthen the internal departments of Universities to enhance the internal cohesion and collective action enthusiasm, promoting the formation of a harmonious environment within the school, and enhance the interaction and contact with the external social institutions. More and more cooperation, strives for more subjects and funds; broaden the channels of information and resources; and form an effective path for the internal and external network. The distribution of resources, effectively improve the quality of students, promote the development of talents, enhance the ability of scientific research, coordinate the relationship between organizations, so as to promote the development of universities. Especially, the structural dimension of social capital provides students with a strong network of relationships, and more training opportunities; to ensure the professional knowledge and skills in the school has a good communication channels and networks for teachers to provide a platform for professional quality training; through the cooperation between universities and the outside world establish more links, providing more diversified sources of funding for the development of Universities, and providing a reference model for the improvement of innovation ability. Thanks to the frequent communication and cooperation, the further improvement of the interpersonal relationship and the relationship network among universities directly promotes the establishment of harmonious environment inside the school.

2.2 Relational social capital in universities

The relationship social capital of universities is reflected as mutual trust among the members of the school, and the trust to universities from the outside social institution. The trust among the internal organizational includes the trust between the leadership and employee, the trust among employees, and the trust to the universities. This kind of mutual trust is similar to Coleman's (1998) view about obligation and expectation. In the process of obligation fulfilling and expecting for compensation, mutual trust is established between the two parties. Both the mutual trust and organizational trust are the core elements of the social capital of universities. Because, on one hand, this trust is expected to be a belief among the school's internal partners; on the other hand, this expectation makes the school members tend to choose cooperative behavior, then they will share their own knowledge and resources, achieving the exchange of resources and restructuring. Moreover, the internal cohesion of the continuous development of cooperation and exchange makes the school members easily subordinate individual goals to collective goals, which make collective action and decision-making more convenient, which is helpful to the realization of the collective goal of the university for the school contribute their own strength. Trust and trustworthiness are two sides of one thing, one side shows trustworthy behavior, and the other will give their trust (Luo Jiade, 2006). Trust is the foundation and premise of other social capital, when the social actions tend to believe each other, trust begins to form in a small range, starting to expand and gradually build up a network of contacts, which promote the formation of social action and consensus. When trust, reciprocity and cooperation form a set of common values and norms, a larger network of relationships begins to form, and the scope of trust began to expand. Trust can make the network more closely, more

unity, communicating and cooperating more efficient. Resources are easier to flow, stronger the cohesion within the school, and the greater the external institution influence. Basing on the existence of trust, the research on the internal and external social capital of university not only has the value of structure, but also the cognitive value. So, the action of social capital of university organization is not only economic benefits, but also has rich concept value and spiritual significance.

The development of universities needs to communicate, contact and interact with other social organizations. With the increase in daily communication, contact and interaction, the exchange of resources and information is produced. Outside the university, the public's respect and trust to universities are helpful to the development of universities. Inside the universities, the trust between the administrative departments and academic teams, between different academic teams is the guarantee of the healthy operation of universities. In addition, the trust between teachers and students is the key to the development of universities. Thus promoting the university's social capital trust is vital to the development of universities.

2.3 Cognitive social capital in universities

On the cognitive dimension, the social capital of universities is mainly represented by language, symbol and knowledge, such as customs, norms, values, beliefs and so on. The establishment of a common vision and common goals can lead people to take action to promote collective interests and bring resources to the organization. A group with common living environment and common language is a group who have certain social resources and control of certain knowledge. It deeply attracts and internalizes a group of people to form a common language and highly recognized social organizations through daily life, similar education. The specification is established during the collective life by extensive implementation of the conduct. It is the behavior standard that university members consider reasonable and acceptable, to promote the internal consensus, coordination and behavior, thereby reducing unnecessary friction and self-serving behavior. The existence of common values will be conducive to the exchange and integration of resources, promoting the organization's common learning, innovation and value creation. The formation of the common faith will be beneficial to the realization of the goal of the team and the formation of the community of interests, which provide a good environment for the development of universities. The common vision will lead all the activities of the organization, creating a sense of unity of the members in the organization, and to unify all kinds of activities. When people do have a common vision, the common vision will gather people together, and produce a cohesive force from the inner driving force, leading members of the organization to gradually achieve the goal (Hou Nairong, 2007).

The goal of the collective development of Universities is based on the internal cohesion and vitality, and this cohesion and vitality is also an important content of University collective goals. Organizing the internal collective activities of universities is the way to enhance the cohesion and vitality of universities. Universities should pay attention to the goal that internal members really want to develop. Otherwise, the realization of the target is time-consuming and laborious, and the operation is inefficient. If the goal is achieved based on shared vision, Individual identity of the overall goal of the school which will form a strong sense of identity. University can mobilize the potential of all aspects, actively communicating, sharing, and putting forward constructive suggestions for the development of the school, to achieve the goal of school development. At the same time, each university members actively participate in the realization of the goal of the development of the university's collective activities, which

increase mutual trust and mutual recognition among people. This help to form a shared language, ideas, and the new link within the school. The whole university will form a closer network relationship, and it will increase the social capital of Universities.

3. The mechanism of how social capital impacts the cultivation of students

3.1 Structural social capital influences the cultivation of students by providing opportunities for social practice

In the network of social relations, weak relationship has more and more space in the modern society because of its characteristics of opening and flowing. The relationship between school and enterprise, school and administration etc. all belong to the category of weak relation. This form of social capital provides convenience for students to participate in social practice. Universities, as a relatively independent organization, need to face the labor market, the enrollment of the student market, and the service market of science and technology. In the diversified social environment, the flow of talent is more and more free and frequent, the traditional family social capital's space and time is greatly limited, social capital of Universities began to play a huge role. To participate in the construction of the structure of social networks, the formation in the relationship between the social capitals with the economic benefits is in the form of externality which can provide students with the opportunity to search for information dissemination channels. The university acts as a bridge to connect alumni and students, teachers and students, industry and students. Developing social capital to provide service for student, students through social network to establish a credible information network, getting training opportunities to improve employment ability. Through the social practice to improve students' social adaptability, social communication ability, competition and cooperation consciousness, student will be of the ability to solve problems by combining professional theory and practical.

3.2 Relation social capital influences the cultivation of students by Club activities

With the increase of the frequency of communication and a series of complex social processes, mutual trust, mutual benefit, cooperation and obligation forms. Then students will improve their interpersonal communication skills, cooperative learning ability, team management ability and honesty, enthusiasm, sense of responsibility, etc.

It is the main way for University students to improve their own quality and realize their development by freely choosing student club, because these student organizations are spontaneously organized by university students. Those clubs meet the common needs of their members and form by the behavior of the members. The student's organizations are the intermediary and bridge between students and schools, social institution. They can help students realize the special development needs in the process of organizational activities and the interaction among members. The formation of beliefs, attitudes, values, academic spirit, behavior patterns, norms, all those are helpful to improve their quality. As a university administrator should fully trust the students, through the formulation designing of the student organization to direct students develop themselves in right direction.

3.3 Cognitive social capital influences the cultivation of students through university culture

The university culture is the creation of the teachers and students in the teaching, scientific research and service society. It is influenced by both traditional Chinese cultural and independent social cultural. It includes not only the concept of a school, professional characteristics, cultural atmosphere, but also the development of the school's

strategic objectives, group awareness, values and behavior norms. University culture, as a kind of experiential, organizational and normative culture, affects Universities students' study and life. Whether the aim of university education can be achieved or not depends on the cultural environment created by the university. The cultural environment of the university has a great influence on the quality of the people educated by the University (Ai Xiaoping, 2006). Through the development of education and propaganda activities, the Universities students should set up the correct world outlook, outlook on life, values, morality, learning, aesthetics, legal system, professional view and talent view. Through the improvement of the knowledge structure curriculum, the talents are cultivated to meet the needs of social development. University's ideological and moral education, public opinion and supervision, as well as the rules and regulations guide Universities students to develop good habits.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, the social capital is divided into structural social capital, relational social capital and cognitive social capital. There are some point put forward that structural social capital influence students by social practices. Relational social capital influence the students by their own organization's activities. Cognitive social capital influences the cultivation of students through the guidance of University culture. Those conclusions have some enlightenment to improve the quality of students and improve their competitiveness through social capital. The problem is that there is no empirical research in this paper. How the three kinds of social capital affect the training of students has not been tested, which is the next work the author need to do.

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